

Y₂SiO₅ AS OXIDATION RESISTANT COATING FOR C/C COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Our proposing coating system that exceeds the current coating system SiO₂/SiC in maximum usage temperature and durability, consists of a rare-earth orthosilicates (Ln₂SiO₅) outer layer for erosion protection and an oxygen diffusion barrier, and a SiC inner layer for a carbon diffusion barrier. The properties desired for an outer coating have been studied about rare-earth orthosilicates (Ln₂SiO₅). Y₂SiO₅ shows low thermal expansion as same as SiC, low evaporation rate and low oxygen permeability. Y₂SiO₅ offers a potential for outer layer of oxidation-resistant coating system.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon (C/C) composites are considered for aerospace applications, because of their low density and superior mechanical strength even at high temperature. But, their oxidation resistance is poor even at temperature as low as 800-900K. So, a developing of a reliable oxidation resistant coating system is required to utilize C/C composites at high temperature. The current coating system of an outer SiO₂ glass and a SiC inner layer of has insufficient performance at temperature exceeding 1800K-2000K, because of low melting point of SiO₂ and chemical instability of SiO₂/SiC interface. We propose a new coating system that consists of rare-earth orthosilicates (Ln₂SiO₅) outer layer for erosion protection and an oxygen diffusion barrier, and a SiC inner layer for a carbon diffusion barrier. Desired properties for the outer layer are thermal expansion compatibility with the inner layer, low evaporation rate and low oxygen permeability. In order to select the outer layer, these properties of some rare-earth orthosilicates were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The rare-earth orthosilicates (Ln₂SiO₅) samples for thermal expansion measurement and evaporation study were prepared from rare-earth sesquioxides (Ln₂O₃) and SiO₂ powders. The

powders were weighed in the desired proportions, mixed by ball milling, cold-pressed and sintered at 1973K for 36ks in air. The materials for oxygen permeation study were prepared from powder synthesized by recrystallization of Si and Y alkoxide mixture. The powder was hot-pressed under 27MPa at 1673K~1723K for 3.6ks~14.4ks. The phases were identified by X-ray diffraction analysis.

Table.1 Characterization of sample

Sample	Base powder (mol%)	Method	Phase observed	Relative density (%)
Y1	50Y ₂ O ₃ +50SiO ₂	sintered	Y ₂ SiO ₅ , Y ₂ O ₃	87.6
YB	50Yb ₂ O ₃ +50SiO ₂	sintered	Yb ₂ SiO ₅ , Yb ₂ O ₃ , Yb ₂ Si ₂ O ₇	88.0
ER	50Er ₂ O ₃ +50SiO ₂	sintered	Er ₂ SiO ₅	89.8
DY	50Dy ₂ O ₃ +50SiO ₂	sintered	Dy ₂ SiO ₅ , Dy _{4,67} (SiO ₄) ₃ O	74.7
GD	50Gd ₂ O ₃ +50SiO ₂	sintered	Gd ₂ SiO ₅	92.6
SM	50Sm ₂ O ₃ +50SiO ₂	sintered	Sm ₂ SiO ₅	85.1
Y21	Y ₂ SiO ₅ from alkoxides	hot-pressed ^a	Y ₂ SiO ₅ , Y ₂ O ₃	93.9
Y22	Y ₂ SiO ₅ from alkoxides	hot-pressed ^b	Y ₂ SiO ₅ , Y ₂ O ₃	99.7
Y23	Y ₂ SiO ₅ from alkoxides	hot-pressed ^c	Y ₂ SiO ₅ , Y ₂ O ₃	96.8

^a at 1673K for 3.6ks in Ar ^b at 1698K for 7.2ks in Ar ^c at 1723K for 14.4ks in Ar

Thermal expansion was measured with push-rod dilatometer in a differential mode between 300K and 1623K for heating and cooling at 0.167K/s. An alumina rod was used as the reference material.

Evaporation rate was obtained by the weight change of sample pellet(8.5mm ϕ \times 1.3mm) after an isothermal heating up to 2223K in air. This experiment was performed by a zirconia heater furnace (Artcor™ model 460-15), and temperatures were measured with a Ir/Rh-Ir thermocouple inserted into the sample stage.

Figure.1 Schematic illustration of oxygen permeability measurement apparatus

Oxygen permeability is defined as a rate of transport of oxygen through a dense, uncrack membrane by diffusion under constant oxygen partial pressure gradient. It was measured by the specially designed apparatus as Fig.1 with a reference to previous work[1]. Test wafers (34.5mm ϕ \times 0.4mm) between the end of weight-loaded Al₂O₃ tubes were sealed with Pt gaskets. Two opposing cells, an upper cell and a lower cell, imposed oxygen potential gradient across the test wafer. This assembly was positioned within a molybdenum heater furnace. The measurement procedure was as follows, (1) heating the test wafer up to 1973K, (2) loading the weight to seal, (3) flowing the gases in the cells for 36ks~180ks to attain equilibrium, (4) measuring oxygen content in lower cell as a function of a temperature with heating up to 2023K and cooling down to 1273K repeatedly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

THERMAL EXPANSION BEHAVIOR

Fig.2 shows the thermal expansion of polycrystalline Ln₂SiO₅ as a function of the temperature. The thermal expansion of Y1,ER1 and DY1 are very low among refractory oxides, and same as that of SiC. Another experiment shows that the Young's modulus of Y21 is about 20GPa at 300K[2], which is much less than other refractory oxides. Consequently, the thermal stress at the Ln₂SiO₅/SiC interface (Ln=Y,ER and Dy) is expected to be suppressed sufficiently.

Figure.2 Thermal expansion of Ln₂SiO₅ and SiC

The thermal expansion coefficients widely vary with rare-earth element as Table.2. It has been reported that Ln₂SiO₅ form two distinct monoclinic structure types depending upon the rare-earth ionic radius[3]. For the larger rare-earth Sm and Gd, the crystal structure of Ln₂SiO₅ consists of two-dimensional O-Ln₄ network and isolated Si-O₄ tetrahedra in the space group C2/c and the thermal expansion coefficients are comparable with that of Ln₂O₃. However, as the radius of the rare-earth ion becomes less than or equal to the ionic radius of Dy, the crystal structure changes to

chain-like $O-Ln_4$ and isolated $Si-O_4$ in the space group $P2_1/c$ and the thermal expansion coefficient drastically decreases below $5 \times 10^{-6}/K$ as Fig.3. This suggests that the difference of the anisotropy of crystal affects the thermal expansion of Ln_2SiO_5 polycrystal.

Table.2 Thermal expansion coefficients of Ln_2SiO_5 and SiC

Sample	Thermal expansion coefficient ($\times 10^{-6}/K$)	
Y1	4.8	(293K-1623K)
YB	5.5	(293K-1623K)
ER	4.8	(293K-1623K)
DY	4.9	(293K-1623K)
GD	7.2	(293K-1623K)
SM	9.3	(293K-1623K)
SiC	4.3	(273K-1600K)[4]

Figure.3 Thermal expansion coefficients of Ln_2SiO_5 and Ln_2O_3 vs. rare-earth ionic radius.

●: Ln_2SiO_5 (measured), Δ \circ \diamond \square ∇ : Ln_2O_3 [5],[6],[7],[8],[9]

EVAPORATION BEHAVIOR

Fig.4 shows weight change of Y1 at 2173K in air. In the beginning, the weight reduces rapidly, but the reduction rate gradually lower. X-ray diffraction analysis on the surface reveals that $Y_{4.67}(SiO_4)_3O$ phase, which is unique to the surface of the starting pellet, disappear after 36ks. This result implies that $Y_{4.67}(SiO_4)_3O$ decomposes to Y_2SiO_5 and SiO_2 , then SiO_2 evaporates. The averaged evaporation rate for initial 36ks is calculated from the weight loss of Y1, ER1 and DY1. The evaporation rates as a function of a temperature are shown as Fig.5. The evaporation rate of Y1 is about $10^{-8}g/cm^2 \cdot s$ at 2173K, and about $0.1\mu m/h$ in converted recession rate. In compared with that of SiO_2 and Y_2O_3 , the evaporation rate of Y1, ER1 and DY1 is close to that of Y_2O_3 rather than SiO_2 . The extrapolated value of evaporation rate vs. $1/T$ line to 2273K is about $10^{-7}g/cm^2 \cdot s$. In the case of a $100\mu m$ -thick coating, this value corresponds to a durability for more than 100h.

Figure.4 Weight change of Y1 at 2173K in air and X-ray diffraction pattern at the surface

Figure.5 Evaporation rates of Ln_2SiO_5 in air

OXYGEN PERMEABILITY

Oxygen permeation consists of three process, namely dissolving into a membrane, diffusing in the membrane and degassing from the membrane. If the diffusion is the rate-determining step, oxygen defect formation at each surface is in equilibrium, and the concentration of oxygen defect is determined by the oxygen partial pressure. In the case of uni-directional diffusion under constant temperature T and constant oxygen partial pressure $p_1(O_2)$ and $p_2(O_2)$ at each surface, oxygen flux P through a plane of unit area is written by

$$P = -D \frac{\Delta C}{l} = -D_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_d}{RT}\right) \frac{[C_2] - [C_1]}{l} \quad (1)$$

where ΔC is a concentration gradient of oxygen defect, l is thickness of membrane, and D is its diffusion coefficient. $[C_1]$ and $[C_2]$ are the concentrations of the oxygen defect at each surface. $[C]$ can be expressed by

$$[C] = k p(O_2)^n = k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_s}{RT}\right) p(O_2)^n \quad (2)$$

where k is equilibrium constant, the exponent n depends on the oxygen defect reaction. Under the condition of $p_1(O_2) \gg p_2(O_2)$, using equation (1) and (2), oxygen permeability constant Pl is written by

$$Pl = D_0 k_0 p_1(O_2)^n \exp\left(-\frac{E_d + E_s}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

In this measurement, oxygen detected in the lower cell contains oxygen penetrated by a gas phase diffusion through openings and pores. Since each penetration mechanism has different temperature dependencies shown in Table.3, oxygen permeation can be separated from other penetration mechanism.

Table.3 Oxygen penetration mechanism and its temperature dependency

Path of penetration	Penetration mechanism	Temperature dependency
openings in cold part	gas phase or Knudsen diffusion	independent
pores ($r^a \gg 0.4\mu\text{m}^b$) in hot part	gas phase diffusion	$\propto T^{1/2}$
pores ($r^a \ll 0.4\mu\text{m}^b$) in hot part	Knudsen diffusion	$\propto T^{3/2}$
oxygen permeation		$\propto \exp(-E/RT)$

^a the pore radius ^b mean free path of oxygen in 101.3kPa at 1873K

Fig.6 shows a typical oxygen concentration in the lower cell as a function of temperature. Oxygen concentration increases prominently above 1600K, obeying $\exp(-E/RT)$ dependency, and remains about 20ppm below 1400K. The residual oxygen concentration can be regarded as oxygen penetration through openings in cold part (C_{g1}), therefore, oxygen concentration C can be expressed by

$$C = C_{g1} + C_p = c_0 + c_3 \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

This curve fairly fits in with measured values between 1200K and 1900K, and oxygen permeability constant is derived from $C_p (=C-C_{g1})$ in equation (4) by

$$Pl = Q \rho_{O_2} \frac{l}{S} C_p \quad (5)$$

where Q is argon gas flow rate in lower cell, ρ_{O_2} is density of oxygen at standard condition, and S is the area of membrane. The oxygen permeability constants of Y21, Y22 and Y23 as a function of temperature is shown in Fig.7. These values are close to that of Y_2O_3 , $ZrSiO_4$, Al_2O_3 and BeO which exhibit the lowest oxygen permeability constant among refractory oxides. In addition, the increasing rate of oxygen permeability constant have a tendency to dull above 1900K.

Figure.6 Typical oxygen concentration in the lower cell as a function of temperature. C_{g1} , C_{g2} , C_{g3} and C_p is plotted under the condition that each plot do not exceed the measured values.

Figure.7 Temperature dependence of oxygen permeability constants at 21.3kPa oxygen partial pressure

Table.4 Oxygen permeability constants of Y_2SiO_5 and refractory oxides

Material	Oxygen permeability constant			Reference
	c_3 (g/cm ³ ·s)	E (kJ/mol)	Fitting rang (K)	
Y21	4.1×10^{-3}	239	1650-1970	this work
Y22	3.3×10^{-3}	232	1330-1900	this work
Y23	5.3×10^{-1}	316	1300-1910	this work
Y_2O_3	4.72×10^{-5}	160	1773-2073	[1]
Al_2O_3	1.21×10^3	450	1823-2073	[1]
ZrO ₂ :CaO	1.24×10^{-1}	233	1382-2333	[12]
ZrSiO ₄	1.32×10^2	392	1635-1833	[12]

SUMMARY

(1) The thermal expansion of Ln_2SiO_5 (Ln:rare-earth) was measured. Ln_2SiO_5 (Ln=Y,Er,Dy) polycrystals exhibited low thermal expansion coefficients, below $5 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, same as that of the SiC inner layer. The thermal expansion coefficients of Ln_2SiO_5 are affected with the rare-earth ionic radius and the crystal structures.

(2) The evaporation rate of Ln_2SiO_5 was obtained by the weight change during isothermal heating. Y_2SiO_5 evaporated at the rate of about $10^{-8}\text{g}/\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{s}$ in air at 2223K.

(3) The oxygen permeability was measured as a function of temperature between 1700K and 2000K. The oxygen permeability constant of Y_2SiO_5 is comparable to that of Y_2O_3 , ZrSiO_4 , Al_2O_3 and BeO which exhibits the lowest oxygen permeability constant among refractory oxides. In addition, the increasing rate of the oxygen permeability constant has a tendency to dull above 1900K.

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